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Computer Assisted Valuation: Multiple Regression Analysis in Cyprus

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Abstract

This paper examines the multiple regression analysis (MRA) valuation system in Cyprus, analyses an empirical application of MRA for houses and apartments in Strovolos Municipality and makes recommendations to the Central Government and the Lands and Surveys Department in Cyprus. The models have been designed to revalue residential properties for taxation purposes at a certain date, with minimum acceptable mean error, minimum data and minimum cost. The coefficient of dispersion (COD) for houses was 10.3% and for apartments 12.3%. These findings compare favorably with other studies and satisfy IAAO criteria for mass appraisal techniques.

Key words: Residential properties, multiple regression analysis, mass appraisal.

Introduction

The basis of General Valuations in Cyprus has been *Capital Value* since the second General Valuation in 1971 in Lefkosia and Ammochostos and was also used in the last General Valuation in 1980 for the whole of Cyprus (except for the area occupied by Turkish troops since 1974). Furthermore, capital value was used after the establishment of the Cyprus Immovable Property (Tenure, Registration and Valuation) Law in 1946 for other purposes e.g. compensation on compulsory acquisitions (Panayiotou et al. 1996).

The Lands and Surveys Department took about twelve years to complete the last General Valuation in Cyprus. Direct Value Comparison (DVC) was adopted and no computerised method or tool was used to assist the process. The long time taken over the revaluation and its high cost are the main reasons why a new revaluation has not taken place in Cyprus since 1980.

It is the contention of the research which underpins this paper, that computer assisted valuations will provide an efficient and appropriate revaluation tool to ensure that Cyprus has an up-to-date base on which the various property-related taxes can be levied, thereby ensuring increased fairness for the tax-paying public. This paper, therefore, investigates the use of multiple regression analysis (MRA) as a tool for implementing a revaluation of taxable residential property within Cyprus and makes appropriate recommendations.

This paper consists of the following main sections: a brief review of applied MRA in property valuation; followed by descriptions of:

- the computer assisted valuation system in the Lands and Surveys Department in Cyprus;
- the study methodology;
- the results; and
- conclusions and recommendations.

A brief review of applied MRA in property valuation

MRA is probably the most popular statistical technique in the business world (Shiffler and Adams, 1995) and it can be argued that it is the most commonly used statistical method for mass appraisal in real estate.

The first and most extensive use of MRA in property valuation was to estimate the open market value of residential property. Pendleton (1965) demonstrated that a statistical model could be constructed to predict the average sales price of a sample of houses in the District of Columbia, within error limits of 6–7 per cent. He commented that it was possible to identify a group of independent variables that could account for approximately 90 per cent of the variations in the selling prices of houses. The principal independent variables used in Pendleton's regression analysis were house size, plot area, accommodation and equipment in the house, a job accessibility index and the mean income of occupants.

Another early application of the method was in the assessment of value for taxation purposes. Hinshaw (1969) as County Assessor of Orange County, California demonstrated how MRA was used to predict the selling price for property using past sales of comparable properties as the basis for prediction. A major claim was objectivity and impartiality in arriving at value. Another advantage demonstrated was low cost and accuracy in assessing the values of a large number of properties very quickly. However a number of valuers remained unconvinced of the benefits of MRA. Lessinger (1969) criticised the way in which MRA was being applied, believing that fundamental assumptions of the method were being violated by the characteristics of the property market.

Adair and McGreal's (1987) analysis of the residential property market in the Northern Ireland Property Market Analysis Project (NIPMAP) indicated that if MRA is to be applied effectively by the valuer then models need to be generated for a "homogeneous" group of properties in a well-defined geographical unit. Furthermore, they explained that in situations where variability is high and spatial location large, such as at the regional or

city scale, it would appear that MRA has severe restrictions, unless good indicators of location can be generated. They concluded that MRA provided valuable assistance to the professional valuer by giving an objectively derived supporting opinion or highlighting circumstances where a re-appraisal of value is necessary.

In a similar study Fraser and Blackwell (1988) commented that the absence of an internal inspection of the houses had prevented the use of about 50 per cent of otherwise reliable sales data. In spite of this, the use of a smaller group of sales and the removal of some variables from the models used, produced a highly satisfactory conclusion (coefficient of dispersion, *COD*, 10.66).

Morch-Lassen and Pedersen (1994) describe a one-step-multi-regression analysis technique used for estimating the value of immovable properties for taxation purposes in Denmark. They showed that for single-family homes, the average error term for the 1986 and 1992 valuations was 2%.

Fibbens (1995) comments that, at the date of his research, simple regression had been the main technique used to produce rating valuations in Australia. South Australia introduced computer-based valuation in 1979 and first used this system in the production of annual values in 1986. Fibbens (*ibid.*) explains that while the use of regression techniques has been favourably reported, the techniques may be subject to some practical problems. Firstly in many cases in Australian valuation practice, all property within a valuation district is valued as at a single base date. However, this is not always the case and it is possible that valuers may be required to report at some other date e.g. the date of inspection of the individual property. Secondly, in cases where regression techniques are used effectively, these are underpinned by an up-to-date, accurate computerised database. Thirdly, in the case of the use of index numbers (sale price/old value), if the original valuation is flawed, a simple linear regression will preserve the flaw throughout the computerised re-valuation cycle. Fourthly, even where an adequate database exists, problems may be encountered in the adoption of computer based valuation systems. It is possible that because of the diversity of housing types in cities such as Sydney, New South Wales that computer approaches developed elsewhere in Australia would be unable to deal effectively with this diversity. Fifthly, the quality of the existing database must be sufficient to support computer based mass appraisal. For example, it may be impossible to predict either annual value or capital value if data relating to improvements is unavailable (or even out of date).

Wayne et al. (1998) describe the use of MRA for the re-appraisal of 4,000 apartment buildings in Alberta, Canada valued using the income approach for the taxation year 1999, using 1998 as the base year. The *COD* of the estimated values was a useful 14.05 and they commented that models should make appraisal sense, be statistically accurate and be stable.

The MRA models that are referred to above are linear. Non-linear models have also produced satisfactory results. In another study, Donnelly (1989) compared three alternatives:

1. the traditional valuation methodology;
2. the linear model; and
3. the Box-Cox (1964) model.

The Box-Cox model is a non-linear transformation of the data that allows the data to indicate the most appropriate functional form. Comparisons among the formulations were based upon an analysis of the values of the log-likelihood functions of the various models. Donnelly concluded that, although the non-linear model formulation produces equation statistics superior to those obtained from the linear model, the latter might well be sufficiently acceptable for the purposes of ensuring the consistency and equity that are intended. Still, as the state of the art in computers progresses, it is probable that even more complex non-linear models, e.g. the quadratic Box-Cox, will become the recommended modeling strategy. However, the linear formulation has proved to be robust and should not be rejected without due consideration. Clearly MRA has a long and respectable pedigree as a tool in residential taxation provided that it is properly applied.

Computer Assisted Valuation Systems in the Lands and Surveys Department in Cyprus

DataCentralen A/S started the development of the Cyprus Integrated Land Information System (CILIS) in 1995, after succeeding in an international tender competition. The development and the testing of the software were completed in June 1999. In July 1999 CILIS was deployed in Strovolos Municipality and progressively will cover the whole Republic. The biggest issue for CILIS is data collection.

DataCentralen A/S proposed the development of the Danish computer assisted mass appraisal (CAMA) system, known as the "Total Value System" or a "Base Home approach", adjusted for the Cypriot situation. However, the Lands and Surveys Department and the DataCentralen A/S (1996a) identified and specified five different valuation methods during the requirement analysis and design stages. The valuation models are designed for use in connection with mass appraisal, as well as valuations for other specific purposes (e.g. compulsory acquisitions) which are known as special valuations. The five methods are:

1. simple regression;
2. direct sale comparison;
3. base home approach;
4. income approach; and
5. cost approach.

The base home approach will be used principally for mass appraisal of residential property areas. It is based on property characteristics and sale transaction evidence and it makes extensive use of MRA.

The critical point for the use of these models is the capturing of appropriate data. If this is not achieved, the various valuation models that have been created will have no application. The valuation models have been designed in an environment of a paucity of data. For that reason it has not been possible to build the models based entirely on the analysis of market evidence but based on assumptions partly derived from experience in other countries, combined with knowledge about the Cyprus market (Morch-Lassen, 1997).

However, the system is flexible, and allows for alternative approaches for each property type. For instance, if it turns out that one approach proves to be wrong when applied, it is possible to exchange the approach for another. Morch-Lassen identified that the base home approach for residential properties contains more than 20 variables (compared to 10 in the Danish system) and warned that the cost of collecting and maintaining data must be considered.

It is worth noting that in an attempt to design a system which actually will perform regression analysis on homogenous areas, base home has been designed to select data for a specific property type from a specific geographical (land value) area, defined by administrative boundaries (district, town, village, quarter), planning zone and location (DataCentralen A/S, 1996b). Location can be any area defined by the responsible valuer. This will cause some problems. Firstly, the system is designed without evidence that homogenous areas can be defined in Cyprus in the above way. Secondly, this approach involves the creation of a large number of separate land value areas and that requires the calculation of a huge number of regression parameters. Thirdly, the creation of a large number of land value areas will limit the application of sales data evidence. The identified problems will make the use of MRA difficult, its efficiency low and effectiveness poor.

Study Methodology

Definition of MRA

MRA is a widely-known method described by various authors (Shiffler and Adams (1995); and Mendenhall and Sincich (1992)). This study adopted the standard multiple regression model;

$$Y = b_0 + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2 + \dots + b_kX_k + e \quad (1)$$

which contains unknown regression coefficients b_1 through b_k as well as b_0 that must be estimated.

A solution to compute b_k is to find the equation of the line that connects the greatest number of sample data points. Alternatively, the estimated regression coefficients $b_0, b_1, \dots, b_k$ that minimise the sum of squares of errors (*SSE*) could be selected and this can be done by the “least squares” method. (*SSE*) is defined as:

$$SSE = \Sigma(Y - \tilde{Y})^2 \quad (2)$$

where Y is the dependent sale price and $\tilde{Y}$ is the predicted value.

Implementing the criterion of “least squares” is difficult without the aid of a computer program. The danger with this process is the dependence on the computer. The computer performs the computation, but it does not propose a model, gather the data, check the assumptions, make the decisions, and so on. If the program is used without critically assessing the inputs and outputs, then all managerial functions are assigned to the pro-

Table 1. Variables collected for houses (H) and apartments (A) or both (HA)

1	Age	HA
2	Block	HA
3	Building condition	H
4	Building type	A
5	Coverage factor of the Planning Zone	HA
6	Date of (contract of) Sale	HA
7	Density factor of the Planning Zone	HA
8	Depth	H
9	Existence of Master Bedroom	H
10	Extra room (office)	H
11	Floor Number	A
12	Frontage	H
13	Geographical code	HA
14	House Type	H
15	House/Apartment size	HA
16	Maximum height of permitted building	HA
17	Maximum number of permitted storeys	HA
18	Number of Apartments in the Building	A
19	Number of floors in the Building	A
20	Number of WC	H
21	Orientation of the house (main entrance)	H
22	Parking Type	H
23	Permitted use of building	A
24	Plot	HA
25	Plot (land) size	H
26	Plot shape	H
27	Relation of building site to road	H
28	Sale price/m ²	HA
29	Sheet/Plan code	HA
30	Street name (code)	HA

gram. Moreover, the validity of the results cannot be assumed if the inputs are not appropriate or inaccurate. A computer program is (in this case) a “means to an end”. It is essential to ensure that the most appropriate “means” is used and that the “means” continues in all cases to provide a useful “end”.

The validity and interpretation of an MRA model depends upon the extent to which certain assumptions are met (IAAO, 1990a).

Methodology

An empirical study in Strovolos municipality (see plans in Appendices A and B) was performed in order to examine and apply regression analysis. Data was collected from 20th October 1994 to 31st October 1997 for 211 houses and 492 apartments corresponding to 64% and 56% of all transactions respectively (See Appendices 2 and 5). The collected variables are displayed in Table 1. The selection procedure is described for those variables where there is a degree of complexity.

The method used for the identification of the variables that contribute to the market value of a residential property in Strovolos municipality was the subject of an interview with a Land Valuation Officer from the Lands and Surveys Department. The result was

the identification of sixty-seven attributes for houses and apartments. Because collection of data is a time- and cost-consuming operation, the collection started as a desk-based procedure. Twenty-five variables for houses and eighteen for apartments were collected. During data collections, care had been taken to gather the most important attributes identified from interviews. These are: location, dwelling size, construction year, size of building site, purchase date and sale price. Local inspections were performed in special cases when a datum was missing in order to complete the sample sets.

Selection Procedure

The age of house (variable 1) was found through the deposited contract of sale or through building permits or by interviewing owners. The variable “age” of the building of apartments was identified through the date of issue of the building permit. There were cases in which the date of issue was not found. In this case, firstly, year of construction was calculated as follows:

$$\text{Year of building construction} = 0.992967 * \text{Year of issue of Division Permit} - 1.275550 \quad (3)$$

and secondly, age was estimated.

The above equation is a result of a simple regression analysis from 124 buildings with standard error 2.18 (3 outliers were excluded).

The building type (variable 4) and the permitted use of building (variable 23) were coded as follows:

1. residential;
2. mixed use residential and commercial.
3. other

The date of sale (variable 6) was calculated in a number of months starting with the date 20/10/94 as follows:

$$\frac{\text{number of days starting from 20/10/94}}{30} \quad (4)$$

Depth and frontage (variables 8 and 12) were recorded manually using a specific scale-ruler from survey plans of Strovolos at scales of 1:2500 and 1:1250. As a consequence a maximum operator error of ± 2 linear meters may occur.

Geographical code (variable 13) is a number that represents the quarters of Strovolos municipality and takes the following values:

1. Chryseleousa;
2. Agios Dimitrios;
3. Apostolos Varnavas;
4. Agios Vasileios.

Size of house/apartment (variable 15) was found from the Lands and Surveys Department's official records or was calculated from sales contract with attached architectural plans (of scales 1:100 or 1:50) using a common scale-ruler applying the following formulas:

$$\text{House size} = \text{Covered Area} + 0.2 * (\text{Uncovered area of Verandas} + \text{Basement area}) \quad (5)$$

$$\text{Apartment size} = \text{Covered Area} + 0.2 * \text{Uncovered area of Verandas} \quad (6)$$

The plot (land) size corresponding to a purchased house (variable 25) was mainly taken from the Lands and Surveys records and plans, but in many cases this was calculated directly from architectural plans (on scales 1:100 and 1:50) using a common scale-ruler.

It is worth noting that all the above variables were scaled. The minimum value was zero and the maximum was 1.3. This permits comparison with a neural network approach that will be reported subsequently.

Outliers

Outliers in multiple regression analysis (MRA) represent cases where estimated values differ from sales prices by unusually large amounts. When regression residuals are normally distributed, two-thirds of sale prices can be expected to fall within one standard error (SE) of their estimated values, 95 percent within two SE, and 99 percent within three SE (IAAO, 1990a). SE is estimated as follows (Shiffler and Adams 1995):

$$SE = \sqrt{\frac{SSE}{n - (k + 1)}} \quad (7)$$

where n is the size of sample and k is the number of independent variables.

It is good practice to examine critically all residuals that exceed a specified amount or percentage of sale price, for example, those that exceed more than two SE (IAAO, 1990a).

The stepwise method (see *next* section) was applied for all the variables of 211 houses and the 492 apartments separately. The variable "Sale price/m²" was used as dependent and the rest of Table 1 as independent. Table 2 shows the regression statistics. Comparing residuals with the SE identified outliers. Seven sales of houses and twenty-two sales of apartments greater than two SE s (0.18678 and 0.1122 CYP*10⁻³ respectively) were identified, and these were classified as outliers. The small number of outliers, 3.3% and 4.5% respectively, suggests that the model fits well.

Multiple R , R^2 and *Adjusted R²* are (AR^2) statistics showing how well models are fitted. Multiple R is the correlation coefficient between the observed and predicted values of the dependent variable. It ranges in value from 0 to 1. A small value indicates that there is little or no linear relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variables. Johnson and Wichern (1992) explain that the sample correlation coefficient is a measure of the linear association between two variables and does not depend on the units of measurements. The sample correlation coefficient, for the i th and k th variables, is

Table 2. Regression statistics of 211 houses and 492 apartments

	Houses	Apartments
R	.63897	.61047
R^2	.40829	.37268
AR^2	.38788	.36622
SE	.09339	.05611

defined as:

$$\bar{X}_i = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{j=1}^n X_{ij} \quad i = 1, 2, \dots, k \quad (k \text{ is the number of variables}) \quad (8)$$

$$r_{ik} = \frac{\sum_{j=1}^n (X_{ij} - \bar{X}_i)(X_{kj} - \bar{X}_k)}{\sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (X_{ij} - \bar{X}_i)^2} \sqrt{\sum_{j=1}^n (X_{kj} - \bar{X}_k)^2}} \quad (9)$$

If the probability is small (.05 or less is often used), the null hypothesis is rejected.

R^2 is a measure of the goodness of fit of a linear model (Norusis, 1993). It is sometimes called the coefficient of determination. It is the proportion of the variation in the dependent variable explained by the regression model. It is also the square of the multiple R , the correlation of the observed and predicted values of the dependent variable.

The sample multiple coefficient of determination R^2 is defined as (Mendenhall and Sincich 1992):

$$R^2 = 1 - \frac{\sum (Y_i - \tilde{Y}_i)^2}{\sum (Y_i - \bar{Y})^2} = 1 - \frac{SSE}{SS_{yy}} \quad (10)$$

There is an estimate of how well the model fits the population (Norusis, 1993). The sample R^2 thus tends to overestimate the goodness of fit of the model in the population. AR^2 corrects the optimistic bias of the sample R^2 taking the sample size and the number of predictors into account. Unlike R , AR^2 does not necessarily increase as additional variables are added to an equation. Mendenhall and Sincich (1992) explain that unlike R^2 , AR^2 takes into account both the sample size n and the number of b parameters in the model. AR^2 will always be smaller than R^2 , and more importantly, cannot be “forced” to 1 by simply adding more and more independent variables to the model. AR^2 is defined as:

$$AR^2 = 1 - \frac{n-1}{n-(k+1)} (1 - R^2) \quad (11)$$

Stepwise method and Time Adjustment

One of the most effective means for mass appraisals is “stepwise multiple regression analysis” (IAAO, 1990a). The stepwise multiple regression method was applied for the

development of multiple regression models of houses and apartments in the Strovolos Municipality. This method selects independent variables for a regression equation. At each step, an independent variable which has the smallest probability of F not in the equation is entered, if that probability is sufficiently small. Variables already in the regression equation are removed if their probability of F becomes sufficiently large. The method terminates when no more variables are eligible for inclusion or removal.

F is calculated as follows (Mendenhall and Sincich, 1992):

$$F = \frac{\sum (Y_i - \bar{Y})^2 / k}{SSE / [n - (k + 1)]} \quad (12)$$

where Y is the dependent sale price and $\bar{Y}$ is the mean value of the sale price.

Under the null hypothesis, this F test statistic has a probability distribution with k degrees of freedom (DF) in the numerator and $[n - (k + 1)]$ DF in the denominator. On the first run of the stepwise MRA with 211 houses and 492 apartments, the following variables were selected:

Table 3. Variables in the first run of the stepwise MRA with 211 houses and 492 apartments

Variable for Houses	Variable for Apartments
Age	Age
Block	Block
House size	Number of apartments in building
Number of WC	Plot
Plot	Size of apartment
Plot (land) size	
Street name (code)	

On the second run, the variables in Table 4 were selected.

Table 4. Variables in the second run of the stepwise MRA with 204 houses and 470 apartments

Variable for Houses	Variable for Apartments
Age	Age
Block	Block
Coverage factor of the planning zone	Number of apartments in the building
Frontage	Plot
Geographical code	Size of apartment
House size	
House type	
Number of WC	
Plot	
Plot (land) size	
Plot shape	

On the third run, the variables in Table 4 with the variable "date of sale" were enforced. The "date" was included for time adjustment purposes.

When real estate markets are changing it is important to adjust sale prices for time in developing an MRA-based valuation model (IAAO, 1978). If the time of a sale is not

controlled, several undesirable results will occur. First, predicted values will lie below current market values in rising markets. Second, regression coefficients will be less stable (i.e., t - and F -values will decline). Third, measures of “good fit” will tend to fall. In addition to being undesirable in and of itself, the latter result has the added shortcoming of making it difficult for the assessor to interpret the regression results. Adjusting sale prices for time tends to produce current market values, improve model stability, improve measures of “good fit”, and facilitate the interpretation of results. In addition, it permits the assessor to utilize older sales, thereby expanding the sample size and/or making possible refined stratification techniques.

Results

Correlation

Tables 5 and 6 show the correlation coefficients (1-tailed significance) of dependent and independent variables for the houses and apartments respectively. The sign “*” on the right denotes that the calculated 1-Tailed Probability is greater than 0.05. Table 5 shows that the most highly correlated variable with the variable “Sale price/m²” of houses was the “plot (land) size”. Furthermore, the parameters “block” and “frontage” affected the sale price/m² of houses considerably. The most highly correlated variable with the variable “Sale price/m²” of apartments is the age. The parameters “apartment size” and “number of apartments in the building” affect sale price/m² considerably.

Statistics

Table 7 shows R , R^2 , and SE derived from multiple regression analysis.

Analysis of Variance

The analysis of variance is used to test the hypothesis that there is no linear relationship between the dependent variable and the independent variable(s). The total variation in the dependent variable is divided into two components, one that can be attributed to a particular regression model (labeled regression), and one that cannot (labeled residual). If the observed significance level for the F -test is small, the hypothesis that there is no linear relationship can be rejected.

Tables 8 and 9 show analyses of variance and display these two sums of squares under the heading “sum of squares”. For regressions, the F statistic was 22.03335 and 60.38629 respectively and the observed significance level (signif F) was less than 0.00005 for both. Thus the hypothesis that the was 0 was rejected for both.

Variables in the Equation

Tables 10 and 11 show the independent variables in the equation derived from regression analysis of the variables shown in Table 4 together with the variable “date of sale”. Beta

Table 5. Correlation (1-tailed significance) for houses

	Sale Price/m ²	Age	Block No	Cover. Factor	Plot size	Front-age	Geogr. code	House type	Plot shape	House size	WC	Date
Sale Price/m ²	1.000											
Age	-.217	1.000										
Block No	.377	-.209	1.000									
Cover. Factor	-.126	.252	-.091*	1.000								
Plot size	.435	.228	.137	-.230	1.000							
Frontage	.295	.045*	.137	-.230	.426	1.000						
Geogr. code	-.076*	-.429	.051*	-.178	.203	-.203	1.000					
House type	-.222	-.202	.312	-.219	.211	.211	.211	1.000				
Plot shape	-.039*	-.209	.074*	-.048*	.262	.262	.262	.262	1.000			
House size	.170	-.475	.115*	-.167	.329	.329	.329	.329	.103*	1.000		
WC	.147	-.639	.003*	-.167	.329	.329	.329	.329	.112*	.329	1.000	
Date	.037*	-.098*	.137	.086*	.037*	-.146	.147	.095*	.015*	.037*	.044*	1.000

Table 6. Correlation (1-tailed significance) for apartments

	Sale Price/m ²	Age	Block No	Num. of Apartments	Date	Plot	Size of Apartment
Sale Price/m ²	1.000	-.495	.210	-.261	-.042*	-.071*	-.305
Age	-.495	1.000	-.097	.271	.120	-.035*	-.102
Block No	.210	-.097	1.000	-.210	.028*	.489	-.031*
Num. of Apartments	-.261	.271	-.210	1.000	.072*	-.041*	-.092
Date	-.042*	.120	.028*	.072*	1.000	.000*	.061*
Plot	-.071*	-.035*	.489	-.041*	.000*	1.000	.040*
Size of Apartment	-.305	-.102	-.031*	-.092	.061*	.040*	1.000

Table 7. Regression Statistics of 204 houses and 470 apartments

	Houses	Apartments
<i>R</i>	.76196	.66257
<i>R</i> ²	.58059	.43900
<i>AR</i> ²	.55424	.43173
<i>SE</i>	.04793	.04425

Table 8. Analysis of Variance for Houses

	Analysis of Variance		
	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Square
Regression	12	.60751	0.05063
Residual	191	.43886	0.00230

$F = 22.03335$ Signif $F = .0000$

Table 9. Analysis of Variance for Apartments

	Analysis of Variance		
	DF	Sum of Squares	Mean Square
Regression	6	.70948	.11825
Residual	463	.90663	.00196

$F = 60.38629$ Signif $F = .0000$

coefficients, sometimes called standardized regression coefficients, are the regression coefficients when all variables are expressed in standardized (Z-score) form. Transforming the independent variables to standardized form makes the coefficients more comparable since differences in the units of measurement are eliminated. These measure the relative importance of individual variables, and thus measure the percentage change in sale price (S) associated with a percentage change in the independent variable (X_j) with all other variables held constant (IAAO, 1990a). Beta coefficients are related to regression coefficients b_j by the following formula:

$$Beta_j = b_j(\sigma_x/\sigma_s) \quad (13)$$

Table 10. Parameters in the equation for houses

Variable	<i>B</i>	<i>SE B</i>	<i>Beta</i>	<i>T</i>	Sig <i>T</i>
Age	-.360697	.048664	-.593586	-7.412	.0000
Plot (land) size	.386437	.044381	.588683	8.707	.0000
House size	-.831863	.108674	-.559654	-7.655	.0000
Block	1.545957	.219417	.383680	7.046	.0000
Geogr. code	-.229217	.041491	-.335677	-5.524	.0000
Number of WC	.291705	.071294	.273779	4.092	.0001
Frontage	.168171	.050702	.189312	3.317	.0011
House type	-.076098	.024940	-.172688	-3.051	.0026
Coverage fact.	.169904	.054930	.163498	3.093	.0023
Plot shape	.040631	.016481	.128138	2.465	.0146
Plot	-.091536	.037857	-.126094	-2.418	.0165
Date	-.003092	.034345	-.004406	-.090	.9284
(Constant)	.272710	.043565		6.260	.0000

Table 11. Variables in the equation for apartments

Variable	<i>B</i>	<i>SE B</i>	<i>Beta</i>	<i>T</i>	Sig <i>T</i>
Age	-.424688	.031804	-.488078	-13.353	.0000
Apartment size	-.628562	.062572	-.354912	-10.045	.0000
Block	.348198	.067177	.213242	5.183	.0000
Plot	-.150584	.033062	-.182793	-4.555	.0000
Numb.of Apart.	-.075060	.021947	-.126974	-3.420	.0007
Date	.023455	.019809	.041748	1.184	.2370
(Constant)	.428355	.011555		37.070	.0000

where σ_x is the standard deviation of the independent and σ_y is the standard deviation of the dependent sale price.

The most important variable in Table 10, related with sale price/m², is the age with the greatest absolute beta coefficient (-0.59358). This means that, with all other variables held constant, a decrease in age of, say, 10% means a younger building will increase the sale price/m² of a house by 5.9%. The second important variable that affects sale price/m² is the plot (land) size (0.58868). An increase in plot size will increase sale price/m². The third important variable that affects sale price/m² is the house size (-0.55965). An increase in house size will increase sale price considerably, but statistically sale price/m² is reduced. The sig *T*, shows that the null hypothesis (that there is no linear relationship between dependent and independents) was rejected, except for the case of the coefficient of the variable "date" of sale, because this had a sig. *T* 0.9284 which is much greater than 0.05. It should be noted that date was enforced in the regression model for time adjustment purposes.

The most important variable in Table 11 is the age of apartment with the largest absolute coefficient (-0.48807). This means that, with all other variables held constant, an increase in apartment age of, say, 10% means older building will decrease sale price by 4.8%. The second most important variable is the apartment size (-0.35491). An increase in apartment size will increase sale price but statistically sale price/m² is reduced. The third most important variable is the block (0.21324).

The sig T indicates that the null hypothesis (that there is no linear relationship between dependent and independents) was rejected, except for the case of the coefficient of the variable “date” of sale, because this had sig. T 0.2370 which is much greater than 0.05. It should be noted that date was enforced in regression model for time adjustment purposes.

Furthermore, both the mean absolute percent error ($MAPE$) and the COD for houses are estimated at 10.3% and for apartments are estimated at 12.3%. The COD for single-family homes and condominiums should be 15.0 or less (IAAO, 1990b). In areas of new or fairly similar residences, it should be 10.0 or less (ibid.). COD s of 10.3% and 12.3% indicate good performance.

The $MAPE$ was calculated as follows:

$$MAPE = \sum_{j=1}^n \left(\left| \frac{S_i - A_i}{S_i} \right| \right) \times \frac{100}{n} \% \quad (14)$$

where n is the number of the sample, S is the sale price and A is the assessment price.

The COD is the most used measure of uniformity (IAAO, 1990a) in ratio studies (A/S). The COD was calculated in respect of the median of the ratio as follows:

$$COD = \frac{100}{median(A/S)} \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n |A_i/S_i - median(A/S)|}{n} \quad (15)$$

Sample Size

MRA has been proven beyond doubt to be capable of generating highly accurate appraisals for residential properties when property data are reasonably accurate and when there are adequate sales (IAAO, 1985). In general, reliable equations can be developed from 100 or more usable sales obtained over no more than a three-year period. The reliability of ratio study statistics depends on the representativeness of the sample (IAAO, 1990a). Representativeness, in turn, is a function of several factors, particularly sample size. In general, the larger the sample, the more reliable the calculated statistics. If ratios are normally distributed, it is possible to calculate the sample size required to estimate measures of central tendency of the population with a given degree of confidence (IAAO, 1990a).

The appropriate formula is:

$$n_r = \sqrt{\frac{(t^2)(COV/100)^2}{h^2}} \quad (16)$$

where COV is the coefficient of variation and is defined as

$$COV = \frac{(100)(\sigma)}{\overline{A/S}} \quad (17)$$

where n_r is the required sample size, t is the t -statistic corresponding to the desired confi-

dence level, h is the tolerance for error expressed as a percentage, σ is the standard deviation and $\overline{A/S}$ is the mean of the assessment sale price ratio.

The value of A/S ratio and the σ were calculated for houses at 1.02 and 0.14 respectively. For a t statistic 2 and a 5% tolerance of error, the COV and the required sample size were estimated at 13.7 and 5.5 cases respectively. The value of $\overline{A/S}$ ratio and the σ for apartments were calculated to be 1.02 and 0.16. For a t statistic 2 and a 5% tolerance of error, the COV and the required sample size were estimated 15.6 and 6.2 cases respectively.

Testing the Normality of Ratio Data

It is often important to determine whether ratio data are normally distributed (IAAO, 1990a). When ratios are normally distributed, the standard deviation and coefficient of variation provide very complete indicators of appraisal uniformity. When ratios are not normally distributed, however, they provide misleading measures of uniformity. In addition, the normality of ratios influences the choice between parametric and non-parametric tests of appraisal performance. When ratios are normally distributed, parametric tests are more efficient. When ratios are not normally distributed, only non-parametric tests are strictly valid. Frequency distributions and histograms are good indicators of the normality of ratio data.

Figures 1 and 2 show histograms of A/S ratio for houses and apartments respectively. These indicate that the distributions are approximately normal. Tables 12 and 13 show the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for A/S ratio for houses and apartments respectively. The observed significance level of 0.1186 for the houses is strong evidence that the distribution of the A/S ratio is approximately normal.

However the observed significance level of 0.0012 for the apartments is not strong evidence that the distribution of the A/S ratio is approximately normal.

The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test is used to determine how well a random sample of data fits a particular distribution (uniform, normal or Poisson). It is based on a comparison of the sample cumulative distribution function to the hypothetical cumulative distribution function. Press et al. (1992) suggest that the Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistic (KS) is a particularly simple measure: it is defined as the maximum value of the absolute difference between two cumulative distribution functions and can be used, for example, for comparing one data set's to a known cumulative distribution function. The statistic is:

$$KS = \max |S_n(x) - P(x)| \quad \text{where } x \text{ is } -\infty < x < \infty \quad (18)$$

Press et. al. (1992) explain that what makes the statistic useful is that its distribution in the case of the null hypothesis (data sets drawn from the same distribution) can be calculated, at least to useful approximation, thus giving the significance of any observed non-zero value of KS .

Testing the normality of the error term

Both Tables 14 and 15 show the Kolmogorov-Smirnov test for residuals of houses and

Figure 1. Histogram of A/S ratio for houses

Figure 2. Histogram of A/S ratio for apartments

Table 12 A/S ratio: Kolmogorov-Smirnov Goodness of Fit Test for houses

A/S ratio- - - - Kolmogorov-Smirnov Goodness of Fit Test

Test distribution – Normal			Mean: 1.02	
Cases: 204			Standard Deviation: .14	
Most extreme differences				
Absolute	Positive	Negative	K-S Z	2-Tailed P
.08321	.08321	-.05340	1.1885	.1186

Table 13 A/S ratio: Kolmogorov-Smirnov Goodness of Fit Test for apartments

A/S ratio- - - - Kolmogorov-Smirnov Goodness of Fit Test

Test distribution – Normal			Mean: 1.02	
Cases: 470			Standard Deviation: .16	
Most extreme differences				
Absolute	Positive	Negative	K-S Z	2-Tailed P
.08893	.08893	-.04667	1.9279	0.0012

Table 14 Residuals of Houses: Kolmogorov-Smirnov Goodness of Fit Test

Residual - - - - Kolmogorov-Smirnov Goodness of Fit Test

Test distribution – Normal			Mean: .00000	
Cases: 204			Standard Deviation: .0459254	
Most extreme differences				
Absolute	Positive	Negative	K-S Z	2-Tailed P
.04804	.04804	-.02769	.6862	.7340

Table 15 Residuals of Apartments: Kolmogorov-Smirnov Goodness of Fit Test

Residual - - - - Kolmogorov-Smirnov Goodness of Fit Test

Test distribution – Normal			Mean: .00000	
Cases: 470			Standard Deviation: 0.0439673	
Most extreme differences				
Absolute	Positive	Negative	K-S Z	2-Tailed P
.02790	.02790	-.02408	.6049	.8578

apartments respectively. The observed significance levels of 0.7340 and 0.8578 are strong evidence that residuals are normally distributed.

Testing the assumption that the error term has constant variance

Both Figures 3 and 4 show that the residuals are randomly distributed for houses and apartments and the variances are approximately constant.

Figure 3. Scatterplot of Residual of houses to Sale Price/square metre

Figure 4. Scatterplot of Residual of apartments to Sale Price/square metre

Conclusions

The following can be concluded for the MRA in Strovolos municipality:

- Good performance; according the IAAO criteria, CODs of 10.3% and 12.3% are acceptable for taxation purposes.
- Objectivity; MRA can measure the importance of the variables objectively where a valuer can not with the traditional methods. In this sense it can be considered superior to results produced by valuers.
- Sensible results; the three most important variables for houses in Strovolos municipality are: age, plot (land) size and house size. In the same way, the most important variables for apartments are age, apartment size and block (location).
- Low cost; the need for twelve parameters for houses and six for apartments, most of which exist in the Lands and Surveys Department, makes the use of stepwise regression analysis cheap in data selection and maintenance.
- Easy use; as soon as the regressors are estimated, SPSS, SAS, database management systems or any other software that can make calculations can be used for mass appraisal, provided that the values of the twelve variables for houses and the six for apartments are given.
- The above application shows that MRA can be applied successfully in Cyprus. It is worth noting that the process followed from data collection and data maintenance, to data preparation and to the clustering of areas is very important to keep MRA efficient, effective, cheap and easy to use.
- The Central Government as well as the Lands and Surveys Department must use this study as a basis for:
 - valuing the importance of each variable;
 - performing data collection to the whole Republic, for revaluation purposes; and
 - performing revaluation for taxation purposes if other methods e.g. non parametric, like neural networks are not proved better.

Recommendations

The following suggestions can be made to the Central Government of Cyprus and the Lands and Surveys Department:

- Similar studies must take place in various municipalities, quarters, towns, improvement boards and villages for each main category of property so as to determine what variables are going to be selected in order to utilize the CILIS-developed MRA models.
- It is necessary to determine the various sources and the various ways of collecting that data at the lowest cost. Use should be made of information technology e.g. image processing, where it is possible.
- Determination of land value (homogenous) areas should be done after statistical analysis. The proposed determination of land value areas at CILIS may lead to a

failure of the MRA because the sale evidence may not be sufficient for each land value area. So the Department must reconsider the determination of those areas.

- Similar studies need to be performed in order to find out where clustering of areas is needed and to examine the possibility of using other methods e.g. neural networks and fuzzy logic, for the identification of the boundaries of (land value) areas.

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APPENDIX 1: List of Abbreviations

<i>A</i>	Assessment
<i>AR₂</i>	Adjusted <i>R square</i>
<i>A/S</i>	Mean of Assessment Sale ratio
<i>b_i</i>	Regression Coefficients
Beta	Standardized Regression Coefficients
CAMA	Computer Assisted Mass Appraisal
CILIS	Cyprus Integrated Land Information System
<i>COD</i>	Coefficient of Dispersion
<i>COV</i>	Coefficient of Variation
CYP	Cyprus pound
DF	Degrees of Freedom
DVC	Direct Value Comparison
<i>e</i>	Error Term
<i>F</i>	<i>F</i> Statistic
<i>h</i>	Error Tolerance (%)
IAAO	International Association of Assessing Officers
<i>k</i>	Number of independent variables
<i>KS</i>	Kolmogorov-Smirnov statistic
<i>MAPE</i>	Mean Absolute Percent Error
MRA	Multiple Regression Analysis
<i>n</i>	Size of Sample (total number of observations)
NIPMAP	Northern Ireland Property Market Analysis Project
<i>n_r</i>	Required sample size
<i>P_(x)</i>	Normal distribution function
<i>r</i>	Coefficient of Correlation
<i>R</i>	Multiple <i>R</i> , Correlation coefficient between the dependent and independent
<i>R²</i>	Coefficient of Determination
<i>S_i</i>	Sale Price
<i>SE</i>	<i>Standard Error</i>
<i>Sig T</i>	Significance of <i>t</i> statistic
<i>S_n(x)</i>	Distribution function of data set
<i>SS</i>	Sum of Squares
<i>SSE</i>	Sum of Square of Errors
<i>t</i>	<i>t</i> statistic
<i>X_i</i>	Independent Variable (observation)
$\bar{X}$	Mean of an Independent Variable (observation)
<i>Y_i</i>	Dependent Variable
$\bar{Y}$	Mean of Dependent
$\tilde{Y}$	Predicted value of Dependent
Z	Standard Score
σ	Standard Deviation

APPENDIX 2

Appendix 2. Plan of Strovolos Municipality with 204 houses

